

THE HARMONY OF FORM AND CONTENT IN THE SONNET

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6010894>

Qayumova Nigora Muxtor kizi

A teacher of ESP for Humanitarian Subjects, Bukhara State University

Annotation: *In this article, the harmony of form and content of the sonnets in English and Uzbek poetry, the peculiarities of the sonnet, the strict laws of the compositional structure of the poem are discussed.*

Key words: *sonnet, literature, genre, compositional structure, form, content, poetry, features of sonnets, poem*

Sonnet (Italian sonare - to sing) is a widespread lyrical genre in world poetry. It first appeared in Italy and then spread around the world. In Italy in the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries Dante, Petrarch, and later Michelangelo, W. Shakespeare in England (XVI century), Mickiewicz in Poland, A.S.Pushkin's sonnets in Russia became world famous. Influenced by Russian literature, the sonnet genre also entered Uzbek poetry. The sonnets of Usmon Nosir and Barot Boykobilov are a worthy contribution to the treasury of Uzbek literature. Traditional-poetic features of the sonnet: the sonnet consists of 14 lines according to the form; The poem consists of two parts in terms of composition: the first part is a two-quartet band, which is called a "quatrain", and the second part is a two-quartet band, which is called a "tercet". Quatrain and tercet are interconnected.

The poetic form requests wonderful opportunities from words to the maximum extent possible, draws attention to the delicate and unique textures of emotions, gives an idea of the state of emotional consciousness. The sonnet is also such a poetic form that, although strictly systematic, in it the emotion is freely expressed, but using laconicism. The specific features of the genre are the strict laws in the compositional structure of the poem, that is, the fact that it has 14 lines, the first four verses are quaternary, the next two triple verses are inverted. In world sonnetics, different forms of rhyming order are observed. This is Italian a-b-a-b a-b-a-b (or a-b-b-a a-b-b-a) c-d-c d-c-d (or c-d-e c-d-e), French a-b-b-a a-b-b-a c-c-d e-e-d and a-b-a-b c-d-c-d e-f-e g-g English forms can be cited as examples. When studying the gradual development of the work of world and Uzbek sonnet writers, we can see that the sonnet, along with other literary events, has improved over the course of time. Style is the unity of all the elements of a work, from the whole

composition to the individual quality mark. In the work of sonnet writers, too, despite the rigidity of the genre, each artist had his own style . Other changes were made to the classical form of the sonnet in later periods.

Uzbek sonnets differ in the interpretation of emotions and the artistic expression of thought. That is, expressive originality is a characteristic of every artist. B. Boykobilov's sonnets reflect almost every situation in the life of the author. This situation is reflected in the calendar poems, hymns dedicated to family members. While acknowledging B. Boykobilov's contribution to the development of the sonnet genre, it should be noted that his sonnets, which consist of forcible difiramb, do not give aesthetic pleasure to the reader. The expression of the various situations chosen by the poet is artistic in nature.

Rauf Parfi's sonnets are distinguished by the variety of themes, the originality of the expression, the unique expressions of poetic thinking . The reason for the poet's appeal to the genre of sonnets is the desire for spiritual perfection, and the desire to follow the path of teachers, as well as to emphasize that perseverance is not only a requirement for the form of the poem, but also a requirement of content and essence. joiz. It can also be interpreted as an attempt to form a complex consciousness in the creative psyche, the ability to control the evolution of the psyche in a strictly legitimate genre. Rauf Parfi, like many great talents, strives for the highest ideals, the highest results. R. Parfi's "Thakurning oxirgi she'ri" ("The Last Poem of Thakur") has a unique compositional structure. The first and second paragraphs of the sonnet give a tercet, the third and fourth paragraphs give a quatrain. This is an example of a "turned" sonnet. The analysis shows that "Qora devor" ("The Black Wall") sonnets follow the traditional compositional principle. It is also noted that in the sonnets of the poet, mainly the quatrain bands are rhymed in the form of a-b-a-b, and the tercet bands in the form of d-e-d, e-d-e.

Fakhriyor's sonnets "Hadik", "Sen meni ...", "Kayfiyat xulosasizligi" and others are as follows:

Na gul bor singrarga otini aytib,
Na kul bor boshingga sochmoqqa zorli,
Na yo'l bor bosh olib ketarga daydib.
What a flower there is,
There's no ashes on your head,
There is no way to stop.

For comparison, let us turn our attention from English sonnets to Shakespearean sonnets. Shakespeare's plays were intended for the general public, and his poems for the less educated students of the time. At the same time, he

wrote the sonnets not for reference to poetry lovers, but for certain people around him. Shakespeare's sonnets can be called lyrical diaries.

In the process of studying Shakespeare's sonnets, you will come across a part of the history of art and literature - the Renaissance - the Renaissance. For Shakespeare, life itself had become a source of knowledge.

It has its own methods of expression. The poet makes extensive use of symbols and allegories in his poems. For example, it resembles youth in spring or dawn, beauty is compared to beautiful flowers. The return of a person's age is like autumn, old age is like winter. The beauty of youth is combined with the charm of summer.

As we read Shakespeare's sonnets, the vitality in it draws our attention, i.e. sometimes the poet uses methods to express his thoughts in such a way that at first glance these metaphors seem to be everyday details. For example:

Sonnet 23

1. A sudden actor in a familiar role.

As if caught, excited,

Great when it comes to anger, not mind

The voice of a lover as if he didn't come out ...

Here, the poet likens a lover who cannot express his feelings to an illiterate actor who forgets his role.

In Shakespeare's sonnets, many vital figurative analogies can be observed. In sonnet 30, the poet describes the trial. Memories of the poet are also present as witnesses to this trial. In the sonnets 46-47, as if the eye of the poet and the argument remain, and reconciles them to the mind. Eventually the eye and the heart come to an agreement. That is, the condition of the agreement is that if the heart wants to see a dear friend, the eyes should bestow this happiness on the heart, if the eyes cannot find a friend, the heart will reward them with memories of the friend's beauty ovuntiri. In sonnet 48, love is compared to a precious treasure, the poet puts it in a box without thinking that it will be stolen, and someone steals it. If we pay attention, every detail has a figurative meaning.

The reason for the richness of the sonnets in metaphors is that the poet was able to read the difficult similarities with the naked eye. His style can be recognized by its beautiful analogies:

Sonnet 33

1. I watched the sun rise at dawn,

Men who wipe the tops of the mountains,

Then he smiled at the emerald meadow,

The water runs on the mercury.

We see that Shakespeare in his poetry skillfully used the art of animation, a common diagnosis in the East. It is the art of transferring human characteristics to inanimate beings. This is manifested in metaphors such as the sun stroking the top of the mountains.

In short, the inter-band consistency of the content of the sonnet, the fact that each verse has the status of an independent poem in the construction of the internal composition is also one of the aspects of the genre in relation to form and content. One of the main requirements of the lyrical composition is the ability to choose the necessary social situation and the desired theme, which is also related to the content of the sonnet genre.

References:

1. Crosland T. The English Sonnet. Hesperides Press, 2006.
2. Literary theory. Two volumes. Volume 1 Literary work. T., Fan 1978.
3. Fuller J. The Oxford Book of Sonnets. Oxford University Press, 2002.
4. Phelan J. The Nineteenth Century Sonnet. Palgrave Macmillan, 2005.
5. Rakhimov A. Shakespeare in Uzbek language / Development of national literature. –Tashkent: Fan, 1981. - P.86-106.
6. Rakhmonova S. Wreath of sonnets and genre development // World literature. - Tashkent, 2008. Issue 1, P. 134-136.
7. Spiller G. The Development of the Sonnet: An Introduction. Routledge, 1992.
8. kizi, Q. N. M. ., & Qayumovich, R. M. . (2021). The Poetics of Colors in English Poetry. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.47494/mesb.2021.16.707>
9. Ro'ziyev, M. (2022). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НЕМЕЦКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ НА ОСНОВЕ ТРЕТЬЕГО ПЕРИОДА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 3(3). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4707

